

Vuzix M4000 Playing media

WATERLINE

Transferring media to your VUZIX

Step 1

Connect your device using a USB-C Cable

Step 2

On Your VUZIX go to 'Settings', Click on 'Connected Devices' and Select 'USB' , Scroll down and select 'Use USB for – File transfer'

Step 3

Your VUZIX will then appear as a drive on your computer, and you can drag and drop files onto it.

Playing media on your VUZIX

Step 1

Swipe forward or backward on the touchpad to navigate through the app carousel until you find the Video Player app.

Step 2

Tap the centre of the **touchpad** to open the Video Player app.

Step 3

Swipe up or down to scroll through the list of available video files in the Video Player app.

Once the desired video is highlighted, tap the centre of the **touchpad** to select and start playing the video.

Step 4

Pause/Play: Tap the centre of the **touchpad** to **pause** the video. Tap again to **play**.

Fast Forward: Swipe forward on the touchpad to **fast forward** the video.

Rewind: Swipe backward on the touchpad to **rewind**.

Adjust Volume: Swipe up or down on the **touchpad** to increase or decrease the volume.